

Systematic Review Protocol for the “Pathogens in Foods”

Database:

Occurrence of relevant *Vibrio* spp. in seafood

Contents

1. Main Objective of the Systematic Review	2
2. Protocol for the Systematic Review	3
2.1 Review question	3
2.2 Criteria for inclusion of individual studies	4
2.3 Searching for individual studies	5
2.4 Deduplication of individual studies	8
2.5 Selecting the individual studies	8
2.6 Assessing the methodological quality	9
2.7 Data extraction from primary research studies	10
2.7.1 General framing data	11
2.7.2 Food characteristics data	11
2.7.3 Outcome data	16
3. Maintenance of the Reference Databases.....	20
4. Modifications to the protocol	20
5. Bibliography.....	20
6. Funding	21
7. Disclaimer	21
8. Annexes.....	22
Annex 1: Search strategies	22
Web of Science	22

<i>PubMed</i>	24
<i>Scopus</i>	27
<i>SciELO</i>	33
Annex 2: PRISMA chart template	36
Annex 3: PIF food categorisation system	37
Annex 4: Categorisation system of methods for relevant <i>Vibrio</i> spp (<i>Vibrio parahaemolyticus</i>, <i>Vibrio vulnificus</i>, <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> non-O1/non-O139)	43
1. <i>Vibrio parahaemolyticus</i>	43
1. <i>Detection assay</i>	43
2. <i>Enumeration assay</i>	44
3. <i>Pathogenicity determination</i>	45
4. <i>Strain characterization (more than Vp or Vpp)</i>	45
2. <i>Vibrio vulnificus</i>	45
1. <i>Detection assay</i>	45
2. <i>Enumeration assay</i>	46
3. <i>Pathogenicity determination</i>	47
4. <i>Strain characterization</i>	47
3. <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> non-O1/non-139	47
1. <i>Detection assay</i>	47
2. <i>Enumeration assay</i>	48
3. <i>Pathogenicity determination</i>	49
4. <i>Strain characterization (non-O1/non –O139)</i>	50

1. Main Objective of the Systematic Review

This protocol is mostly based on the protocol titled “Review Protocol for the "Pathogens in Foods" Database: Prevalence and Concentration of Main Biological Hazards in Food Matrices” that has been published on Zenodo as a deliverable from the GA GP/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01 (<https://zenodo.org/record/7741392>). The main objective of this systematic review is to identify and extract, under a categorised arrangement, information and data on the occurrence (*i.e.*, prevalence and concentration) of *Vibrio* spp. of public health importance (*i.e.* *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, *Vibrio vulnificus*, and *Vibrio cholerae* non-O1/non-O139) in seafood produced and/or commercialised in Europe. Data periodically obtained from peer-reviewed articles will

feed the web application *Pathogens in Foods* (<https://pif.esa.ipb.pt/>) through a dedicated database insertion system (<https://pathogens-in-food-frontend.vercel.app/>).

The present systematic review protocol will be employed to retrieve published studies and data in the following periods:

Search of September 2023: Covering studies published between January 2010 and September 2023.

Search of September 2024: Covering studies published between January 2000 and January 2010 and between September 2023 and September 2024.

Search of September 2025: Covering studies published between September 2024 and September 2025.

Search of January 2026: Covering studies published between September 2025 and January 2026.

2. Protocol for the Systematic Review

2.1 Review question

The review question is: “what is the occurrence (*i.e.*, prevalence and concentration) of *Vibrio* spp. of public health importance (*i.e.*, *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, *Vibrio vulnificus*, and *Vibrio cholerae* non-O1/non-O139) in seafood produced and/or commercialised in Europe. This descriptive question has a simple PO (*population* and *outcome*) structure with key elements that can be broken down, as follows:

Population: Seafood and composite foods containing seafood produced and/or commercialised in Europe

Outcome: Occurrence of at least one of the following hazards: *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, *Vibrio vulnificus*, and *Vibrio cholerae* non-O1/non-O139 expressed as either prevalence or concentration measured in the population.

Because both key elements can be clearly specified, the review question is *close*-framed, which is advantageous because it enables the setting of more clear eligibility criteria *a priori*, as opposed to open-framed questions.

2.2 Criteria for inclusion of individual studies

For a study to be included in the systematic review, it should comply with criteria related to study characteristics (*i.e.*, at the levels of study design and setting, population, outcomes of interest, and method used), and criteria related to report characteristics (*i.e.*, type of publication and language of the full text). The eligibility criteria are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Eligibility criteria for inclusion of individual studies in the systematic review

Type of criteria	Eligibility criteria
<i>Criteria related to study characteristics</i>	
Study design and setting	[1] Occurrence data must originate from observational studies that could be cross-sectional or longitudinal where food units have been sampled by a randomised design, either simple or stratified.
Population	[2] Seafood and composite foods containing seafood commercialised in Europe, as finished product or during production/processing, must be sampled from primary production, processing facilities, retail or restauration establishments. [3] Food chain stage where samples were taken must be specified.
Outcomes of interest	[4] The study must present results on prevalence and/or enumeration of <i>Vibrio parahaemolyticus</i> , <i>Vibrio vulnificus</i> , and <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> non-O1/non-O139 in seafood and composite foods containing seafood [5] For prevalence, it should provide at least <i>sample size</i> and <i>number of positive samples</i> ; and for enumeration, it should provide at least the <i>sample size</i> and <i>a measure of concentration</i> .
Method	[6] The microbiological method used must be indicated, or alternatively a reference provided; and the sample size must be higher than 3 units.
<i>Criteria related to report characteristics</i>	
Language of the full text	[7] English, Spanish, French, Portuguese (all searches) and also Italian and German (search of September 2023 only)
Publication type	[8] Primary research studies and reviews

Data in graphical format

The inclusion of a primary research study whose results are presented in graphical format will be decided on a case-by-case basis. It will depend on how feasible and reliable the extraction of data from the charts is.

Examples of primary research studies excluded

Primary research studies not meeting the pre-set criteria will not be included in the systematic review. Examples of primary research studies that will be excluded are: (1) reports of pathogens' counts from likely food vehicles within the context of investigation of foodborne outbreaks; (2) studies providing occurrence data without pointing out the microbiological method used or at least citing an informative source in the list of references; (3) studies that do not provide the amount or unit of analytical sample used in the detection assay either directly in the methodology description or in the references.

2.3 Searching for individual studies

The bibliographic search will be conducted using a combination of general terms, biological hazards, foodstuffs and countries.

General terms (Title-Keywords-Abstract):

“microbial quality” OR “microbial safety” OR “microbiological quality”
OR “microbiological safety” OR analyses OR analysis OR concentration
OR contamination OR count* OR detection OR enumeration OR
incidence OR investigation OR occurrence OR presence OR prevalence
OR sampling OR survey*

Pathogen (Title-Keywords-Abstract):

“Vibrio parahaemolyticus” OR “Vibrio vulnificus” OR “V
parahaemolyticus” OR “V vulnificus” OR ((Vibrio OR cholerae)
NEAR/3 (non-O1 OR non-O139 OR nonO1 OR nonO139 OR non-01
OR non-0139 OR non01 OR non0139))

Foods (Title-Keywords-Abstract):

Seafood:

seafood OR seafoods OR “sea food” OR “sea foods” OR crustacean* OR
shellfish OR bivalve* OR mollusc* OR mollusk* OR fish* OR finfish
OR “fishery product*” OR “marine gasteropod*” OR cephalopod OR
cephalopods OR crustacean OR crustaceans OR echinoderm OR
echinoderms OR “sea urchin” OR “sea urchins” OR holoturid* OR
tunicate OR tunicates OR urchin* OR crab* OR prawn* OR shrimp* OR
lobster* OR “crayfish” OR crabfish OR crawfish OR langoustine OR
scampi OR “clam” OR “clams” OR “carpet shell*” OR scallop* OR
Pecten OR oyster* OR cockle OR cockles OR mussel OR mussels OR
mytilus OR “Pen shell*” OR snail* OR abalone* OR Nassarius OR
“whelk*” OR Bolinus OR “murex” OR ormer OR Haliotis OR “true

limpet*” OR Patella OR Cellana OR Buccinum OR Concholepas OR conch* OR winkle* OR periwinkle* OR octopus OR squid* OR cuttlefish OR nautilus* OR Todarodes OR Loligo OR Sepia OR Paracentrotus OR Strongylocentrotus OR “Echinus esculentus” OR “sea cucumber*” OR “cukes” OR piure* OR pyura OR “sea violet*” OR “sea tulip*” OR “sea peach*” OR “sea pineapple*” OR “ice floe” OR “sea squirt*” OR gravad OR graved OR "gravad lax" OR gravlax OR sushi OR sashimi OR surimi OR ceviche OR caviar OR albacore OR amberjack OR anchovy OR anchovies OR angler OR anglerfish* OR anguilla OR argentine OR Argyrosomus OR bacha OR barbel OR barracuda OR basa OR bass OR beluga OR bib OR bigeye OR blackfish OR bleak OR blenny OR bluefish OR “blue runner” OR “blue shark” OR bonito OR branzino OR bream OR brill OR burbot OR butterfish OR Capellin OR carp OR catfish OR catshark OR “Chelon auratus” OR chub OR “clupea harengus” OR cod OR comber OR conger OR corb OR cutlassfish OR cyclopterus OR Cyprinus OR cyprinidae OR dab OR “danubian wels” OR dentex OR dicentrarchus OR dogfish OR eel OR emperor OR engraulis OR flathead OR flounder OR “flying fish” OR forkbeard OR gadus OR garfish OR garrick OR goby OR goldline OR grouper OR guitarfish OR gunard OR haddock OR hake OR halibut OR hammerhead OR herring OR hippoglossus OR hoki OR huss OR icefish OR “John dory” OR “Katsuwonus pelamis” OR labrus OR lamprey OR lanternfish OR leerfish OR ling OR “little tunny” OR “Liza aurata” OR lophius OR lumpfish OR lythe OR mackerel OR “mahi mahi” OR “mallotus villosus” OR marlin OR meagre OR megrim OR melva OR merluccius OR Micromesistius OR monkfish OR moonfish OR mugil OR mullet OR “mullus barbatus” OR needlefish OR Oncorhynchus OR oreo OR osmeridae OR pacu OR pandoras OR panga OR pangasius OR parrotfish OR “parrot fish” OR perch OR picarel OR pike OR pikeperch OR pilchard OR pilotfish OR “pilot fish” OR platicthys OR plaice OR pleuronectes OR pollan OR Pollack OR Pollock OR ponyfish OR porbeagle OR pout OR pouting OR ray OR ribbonfish OR rigg OR rockfish OR rofefish OR sablefish OR sailfish OR salmon OR salmo OR sandeel OR sardine OR sardina OR sardinella OR scabbardfish OR scomber OR scophthalmus OR scorpionfish OR “sea bass” OR seabass OR seabream OR “sea bream” OR seriola OR sheatfish OR “shi drum” OR sild OR sillago OR skipjack OR smelt OR smooth hound OR “smooth-hound” OR snapper OR snook OR sole OR solea OR sparidae OR sparus OR sparring OR spearfish OR sprat OR sprattus OR “St Peter’s fish” OR stargazer OR stingray OR stizostedion OR sturgeon OR “surgeon fish” OR trachurus OR swordfish OR tailor OR tench OR theragra OR thunnus OR tilapia OR tinca OR threadfin OR triggerfish

OR trisopterus OR trout OR tubefish OR tuna OR turbot OR tusk OR walleye OR weever OR whitebait OR whiting OR wrasse OR yellowtail

Seafood Composite: meal OR meals OR food OR foods OR “buffet meal*” OR “complex food” OR “frozen meal*” OR multi-ingredient OR “multi ingredient” OR ready-to-eat OR RTE OR “ready meal” OR “ready prepared” OR “ready to eat” OR “under vacuum” OR composite* OR convenience OR cured OR dip OR dips OR dish OR dishes OR dressing* OR dumpling* OR fermented OR filling OR gravy OR macerated OR marinad* OR marinate* OR mayonnaise OR pasta OR pizza OR pickled OR preserved OR pudding* OR puree* OR salsa OR salsas OR salted OR sandwich* OR sashimi OR ceviche OR sauce* OR smoked OR snack OR snacks OR soup OR soups OR stew* OR surimi OR sushi OR topping* OR chowder

European countries : (Affiliation) OR (title-Keywords-Abstract)

Albania OR Andorra OR Armenia OR Austria OR Azerbaijan OR Belarus OR Belgium OR Bosnia and Herzegovina OR Bulgaria OR Croatia OR Cyprus OR Czech Republic OR Denmark OR England OR Estonia OR Finland OR France OR Georgia OR Germany OR Greece OR Hungary OR Iceland OR Ireland OR Italy OR Kazakhstan OR Kosovo OR Latvia OR Liechtenstein OR Lithuania OR Luxembourg OR Macedonia OR Malta OR Moldova OR Monaco OR Montenegro OR Netherlands OR North Macedonia OR Norway OR Poland OR Portugal OR Romania OR Russia OR San Marino OR Serbia OR Slovakia OR Slovenia OR Scotland OR Spain OR Sweden OR Switzerland OR Turkey OR Türkiye OR Ukraine OR United Kingdom OR UK OR Vatican OR Wales OR Yugoslavia OR Europe* OR EU OR Faroe*

AND NOT Terms (Title-Keywords-Abstract):

“*in vitro*” OR “*in-vitro*” OR “challenge study” OR “essential oil*” OR attribution OR biofilm* OR “plant extract” OR “extracts” OR feed OR livestock OR sanitiser OR sanitizer OR spiked OR “feed supplement*”

Articles will be searched in the e-bibliographic databases PubMed, Web of Science Core Collection, (Science Citation Index Expanded and Emerging Sources Citation Index), Scopus and SciELO (<https://scielo.org>) (see **Annex 1**), using the aforementioned terms duly connected (General terms AND pathogen AND Food (seafood OR composite) AND NOT Selected terms) and in the proper database syntax. The entries will be filtered by database insertion date (according to the search periods specified in Section 1), type of publication (only primary research

articles and reviews) and languages (English, Spanish, French and Portuguese¹). For the first bibliographic search in 2023 (AFFILCOUNTRY) OR (Title-Keywords-Abstract) Italian and German papers will be added to languages; support for the data extraction will be given by the members of the EFSA *Vibrio* in seafood Working Group dealing with the self-task mandate of the BIOHAZ Panel on the public health aspects of *Vibrio* spp. related to the consumption of seafood in the EU (EFSA-Q-2022-00826²). Date of searches and number of records retrieved will be duly documented. The bibliographic search process in the four databases will be carried out by two researchers working in parallel and on the same day, who will then compare the number of records recovered, which should duly match in order to proceed with the next steps.

2.4 Deduplication of individual studies

The volume of bibliographic citations will be documented and managed in a project built on DistillerSR software, which will be set to identify duplicate references. Duplicates from the PubMed, Web of Science Core Collection, (Science Citation Index Expanded and Emerging Sources Citation Index), Scopus and SciELO will be carefully checked and deleted/merged by the two researchers.

From the volume of deduplicated citations, reviews and systematic reviews will be identified and their list of references will be downloaded to a separate project and filtered by a temporal boundary. If those reviews identified relevant original papers, they will be added to the database and flagged as coming from an identified review source.

Records will be kept in one single reference database. The reference databases will be managed by two senior experts in systematic reviews, who will ensure maintenance and updating of the databases at the different stages of the review process.

2.5 Selecting the individual studies

The whole process of selection of individual studies will be carried out by two trained reviewers and two senior reviewers. Once all the entries have been deduplicated, relevant studies will be screened for inclusion by one trained reviewer. In case a new staff member joins the project, training in SR and a pilot will be conducted by the senior reviewers. Doubts on the inclusion of a study will be resolved in the regular meetings with the senior reviewer(s). Three steps will be followed:

¹ Only these additional languages are considered for being the working languages of the IPB-Anses team.

² <https://open.efsa.europa.eu/questions/EFSA-Q-2022-00826>

- a. *Title/abstract (Ti/Ab) screening.* Each of the titles and abstracts from the bibliographic databases will be screened for its relevance to answering the review question. The number of records that did not pass this first screening or remained unclear will be annotated.
- b. *Examining full-text reports.* Records that pass the Ti/Ab screening and those that remain unclear will undergo an examination at full-text level. Each full-text reference will be screened for eligibility based on record and study characteristics, according to the inclusion criteria outlined in Section 2.2. All annotations relative to the inclusion criteria, study characteristics and outcome data will be made in the environment of the DistillerSR project.
- c. *Identification of possible duplicate publications.* Because sometimes the same study is reported or partially reported in two or more articles, these situations must be carefully identified to avoid double-counting. Records likely to be linked to the same study will be marked in the DistillerSR project for posterior evaluation, in discussion with one of the senior reviewers. If the evaluation of results points towards the case of a duplicate publication, the linked records will be grouped and examined as one study unit.

Each stage of the study selection process will be well documented, in order to make it (re-)assessable. The number of studies eligible for inclusion will be annotated, while, for the studies excluded at the full-text report level, the reasons for exclusion will be provided. To register the flow of the number of literature records along the different phases of the systematic review, a PRISMA chart will be used. A PRISMA chart template can be found in **Annex 2**.

2.6 Assessing the methodological quality

Each eligible primary research study will undergo a quality assessment. The results of a study will be signalled as *having potential for bias* if there is any suspicious of:

- a. *Selection bias:* in situations where there is a suspicion that proper randomisation of the food units was not achieved. For instance, when sampling was undertaken in the context of a monitoring program/surveillance implemented after an outbreak, or microbiological analysis of food sampled at retail but close to the end of shelf life.
- b. *Aggregation bias or reporting bias:* Prevalence or enumeration results are combined for distinct food classes within the same food category or combined for samples from different food chain stages (for instance: prevalence data combined for mixed commercial species as oysters/mussels).

- c. *Detection bias*: The outcomes of a study will be signalled as being potentially biased if any of the following two situations arises:
- c1. Detection and/or quantification of the hazard pathogens not undertaken using an approved (clearly “defined” or “codified” (meaning that it refers to a method whose procedure has been described in a formal way (as ISO or BAM) or known microbiological method, or the method is not fully described (either in the study or in the reference publication) and except the limit of detection or quantification.
 - c2. Amount (weight, volume, surface or whole unit) of the analytical sample is not explicitly indicated in the study, but assumed from authors’ previous publications, from the range of analytical sample amount provided in the text or taken from manufacturer’s instructions in case a kit was used.
 - c.3 *Vibrios not fully identified* (*Vibrio* spp. or *Vibrio* non-O1 or *Vibrio* non-O139). Incomplete identifications with papers providing results for “non-O1” but not checking O139.
- d. *Quality of reporting*: In cases of lack of concordance between results presented in the text and those compiled in the table(s), the ones presented in tabular format will be taken, and the results marked as potentially biased, or estimates calculations not clear.

The results taken from studies that present at least one of the aforementioned validity threats will be marked as potentially biased, in order to perform sensitivity analysis at a later stage during meta-analysis. Meeting more than one potential-for-bias criterion will not be considered sufficient to discard a study. Every study will undergo quality assessment by one reviewer, who, when in doubt, will consult with the second reviewer. Where there is no consensus, the senior reviewer(s) will resolve doubts on methodological quality assessment, and furthermore they will corroborate the correctness of the status of those studies marked as being potentially biased.

2.7 Data extraction from primary research studies

The data to be extracted are related to (i) general framing of the study, (ii) study characteristics relevant to explain heterogeneity in the outcomes, namely the nature of the food sampled and the method of detection/quantification, and (iii) outcome measures, detection and/or quantification.

The data extraction form is in Excel format. The data extraction will first be carried out using Excel for the eligible studies. Further on, the extracted data in Excel format will be automatically

fed to the PIF database. For negative results, the relative species with negative results will be extracted in the database if this species is clearly mentioned in the text or in the Table.

The different proposed fields of the data extraction are given below and underlined in yellow. Some minor changes in the type of fields can occur after testing for first publications extractions. Some minor changes could be done in agreement with the EFSA *Vibrio* in seafood Working Group.

2.7.1 General framing data

Study ID: Unique identifier of the study. StudyID follows the rule: “FirstAuthorSurname_AbbreviatedJournal_PublicationYear”.

Study type: (a) Survey, for studies whose objective was to characterise or investigate the microbiological safety of food, or its compliance to legislation; (b) Comparison, for studies comparing methods of detection of pathogens; and (c) Other, for any other type of study.

Country of publication: country of the institutional address of the corresponding author.

Year: starting year of the sampling.

Study duration: duration of the sampling in months.

2.7.2 Food characteristics data

The following study characteristics describe the food sample.

Country of sampling: country where the food was sampled.

Country of origin: country of production/processing of the food if stated in the study as different from the country of sampling.

Country of consumption: Country where the food is consumed (if specified in the publication) (*export for European countries*)⁴

Packaged status: (a) Yes, for samples of food in any type of packaging. If food is packaged, the class “In air”, “In modified atmosphere”, “Vacuum-packing” or “Unknown packaging material”

⁴ Will be done in excel FILE, see later if relevant to be introduced in PIF database

should be selected to indicate normal atmosphere package, modified atmosphere package, vacuum package or other type of packaging, respectively; (b) No, for food samples without packaging, (c) Various, for samples of food that were both packaged and unpackaged, and (d) NA (not available), when the study does not indicate the packaging status of the food or cannot be reasonably deduced.

Sampling stage: refers to the stage of the food chain from which the sample was extracted: (a) Primary Production, (b) Manufacturing, including any processing stage within the reception of raw materials and the end of processing, and (c) Distribution, entailing:

- Storage, when food products are sampled at the end of production
- Retail, when food products are sampled at any retail establishment or vending machines
- Restaurant, when sampling is carried out at restaurants or catering services.

Code	Name
E100A	Primary production → Commercial landing
E100A	Primary production → Farmed (commercial)
E100A	Primary production → Farmed research setting
E100A	Primary production → Research fishing
E100A	Primary production → Commercial fishing
E100A	Primary production → Harvesting
E100A	Primary production → NA
E300A	Manufacturing
E500A → E700A	Distribution: wholesale and retail sale → Storage
E500A → E520A	Distribution: wholesale and retail sale → Retail

E500A → E910A	Distribution: wholesale and retail sale → Restaurant
------------------	---

Point of sampling (precision for above (a) Primary production, adding more choice fields) it refers to the precise origin of the sampling point if “Harvesting (shellfish)” is selected.

- **Commercial**
 - Classification of marine area (shellfish) A, B, C or NA (non informed)
 - Before or after mandatory purification (shellfish) (relevant for products from B and C classified area) or NA (non informed)
 - Before or after mandatory relaying (shellfish) (relevant for products from B and C classified area) or NA (non informed)
- recreational
- other (e.g. research or illegal)
- Other

Production method: Indicates if the seafood is wild or from aquaculture farm : wild/farmed/NA

Fishing or harvesting area of origin: It refers mostly to the FAO area , approximated from the map or site name given in the publication, (to see correspondence the FAO website *i.e.* <https://www.fao.org/fishery/en/area/87/en>)

Geographical area: refers to the production level

- **FAO area** : refers to FAO area where the samples were fished
- **FAO subarea** refers to FAO subarea where the samples were fished
- **FAO division** : refers to FAO division where the samples were fished
- **FAO subdivision** refers to FAO subdivision where the samples were fished
- **Unit FAO** refers to FAO unit where the samples were fished

Marine Coordinates (in WGS 84 projection system)

- **Latitude:** refers to the latitude in decimal degrees (if given in publication) or NA
- **Longitude** the longitude in decimal degrees (if given in publication) or NA

Geographical Label : the description of the geographic area as indicated in the study (as precise as possible in the publication example : “Wadden sea”, name of landings e.g “port de la Rochelle”...)

Temperature at sampling: refers to the temperature class of the food when sampled.

(a) Ambient temperature (primary production mostly) in °C⁵ (Range

- a. Min value
- b. Max value
- Mean: value
- Median: value
- NA

(b) Chilled,

(c) Frozen,

(d) Various,

(e) Not available.

Salinity at sampling: Salinity will be expressed in number of grams of salts per kilogram of seawater, which is expressed in parts per thousand, if sampling at primary production level⁶

- Range
 - a. Min value
 - b. Max value
- Mean: value
- Median: value
- NA

Month of the beginning of sampling (as most precise as possible in publication) (full date or by default the first day of the month or NA)

Month of the end of sampling (as most precise as possible in publication) full date or by default the first day of the month or NA)

RTE status: refers to whether the food produced or being produced is ready-to-eat (Yes) or non-ready-to-eat (No).

Type of food: the food is categorised utilising the hierarchy system (details in Annex 3) comprising:

- Category,
- SubCategory,
- FoodClass
- FoodSubClass
- ClassSpecie

⁵ Will be done in excel FILE, see later if relevant to be introduced in PIF database

Food label: is the description of the food sample as indicated in the study (ex latin name + commercial name in bracket; if not latin name commercial name only).

For all above fields: from the Latin name given in the publication (by example *Crassostrea gigas*), a search from WoRMS (<https://www.marinespecies.org/>) will be used to update the latin name with the current marine organism classification (by example *Magallana gigas*). The different levels of classification are deduced from WoRMS database.

Species of seafood: Latin name provided/checked from WoRMS (or NA)

Genus of seafood: refers to the genus of seafood(s) provided from WoRMS (or NA)

Family of seafood: refers to the family of seafood(s) from WoRMS (or NA)

Order of seafood: refers to the Order of seafood(s) provided from WoRMS (or NA) ⁶

Foodex2 code: correspondence Foodex2 code

Common name and Latin names corresponding to Foodex2: refers to the common name from Foodex2 (official name in English, e.g rainbow trout) (from the Latin name with Foodex2 correspondence or economic /vernacular name).

Organ sampled: When the sample is fish, information must be provided as to the organ sampled, which can be: digestive tract, stomach, bowel, whole fillet, belly flap, fillet without belly flap, visceral cavity, gonads, liver, whole fish, gutted fish or other. When the sample is mollusk: whole flesh, digestive gland, haemolymph.

Characteristics for bacteria

Species: refers to the species of the *Vibrio*

- *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*
- *Vibrio vulnificus*
- *Vibrio cholerae*
 - Non-O1 AND non-O139
 - Non-O1 (bias)
 - Non-O139 (bias)

⁶ Will be done in excel FILE, see later if relevant to be introduced in PIF database

Label pathogen /Serotype/serovar/other: refers to the serotype, serovar, strain, or any other distinct variation within a pathogenic bacterium, most precise item as mentioned in publication. It is an open field.

AMR results in the publication

- Yes/no

Characteristics for methods

The detailed methods for each type of pathogen are given in **Annex 4**.

2.7.3 Outcome data

The outcome data are of five types: general results, prevalence results, enumeration results, and pathogenicity and strain results (presence of antimicrobial results in study characteristics data).

General results

Sample weight unit: is the unit in which the amount of analytical sample is expressed: (a) g, (b) ml, (c) cm², or (d) unit. Unit refers to the analysis of one entire unit, for instance, one strawberry/one oyster subject to analysis.

Number of units in the pool (if pooled analysis) (and if units)

Total units tested (ex. **Number of samples**): refers to the number of samples submitted for analysis. It corresponds to the metrics of EFSA data models “Total units tested”.

Pathogenicity Confirmation : It refers as to whether the detected or enumerated pathogen was subjected to pathogenicity test (Yes) or not (No). When no information is provided, the class NA is used.

Total units tested (ex. **Number of samples**): refers to the number of samples submitted for analysis of prevalence. It corresponds to the metrics of EFSA data models “Total units tested”.

Prevalence results

Sample weight detection: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the detection assay (in sample weight unit).

Limit of detection (LoD): limit of detection of the method if given in the study in log CFU per g, ml or cm². Or NA if not known

Detected samples: number of positives samples;

Prevalence in %: $\frac{\text{number of positive samples}}{\text{total units tested}} \times 100$ (2 decimals)

Enumeration results

Sample weight enumeration: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the enumeration assay (in g)

Number of samples used for enumeration

Type of calculation: on positive samples only /on possible positive and negative results (prefer the first type in case of choice)

Counts unit: It is the unit in which the counts are given: raw numbers per sample weight unit, log base 10 numbers per sample weight unit, or natural logarithm of the numbers per sample weight unit.

Counts model:

LOQ : limit of quantification of the enumeration assay in log CFU per g, ml or cm². Or NA if not known

- On positive samples only (type of calculation of the mean)
 - Impute: LOQ
 - Non impute, if no LOQ considered, and only quantified samples were used to calculate the mean
 - Impute: other +text
- On possible positive or negative results (type of calculation of the mean)
 - Non quantified samples and/or non detected imputed to zero
 - Non quantified samples and/or non detected imputed to LOQ
 - Non quantified samples and/or non detected imputed to LOD
 - Impute: Other+text

Greater than LoQ: number of “positive” samples (greater than the LoQ). **NA if not known**

Lower than LoQ: number of “negative” samples (lower than the LoQ). **NA if not known**

In all below, Replace LOQ by minimum value quantified if LOQ not given. Log is Log10.

[LoQ – 1]: number of samples whose counts are between LoQ and 1 log CFU per g, ml or cm², if LoQ is lower than 1 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[LoQ/1 – 2]: number of samples whose counts are between LoQ and 2 log CFU per g, ml or cm², if LoQ is between 1 and 2 log CFU per g, ml or cm²; or number of samples whose counts are between 1 and 2 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[2 – 3]: number of samples whose counts are between 2 and 3 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[3 – 4]: number of samples whose counts are between 3 and 4 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[4 – 5]: number of samples whose counts are between 4 and 5 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[5 – 6]: number of samples whose counts are between 5 and 6 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[6 – 7]: number of samples whose counts are between 6 and 7 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

[7 – 8]: number of samples whose counts are between 7 and 8 log CFU per g, ml or cm².

Min concentration value

Max concentration value

Mean concentration: mean concentration of the hazards in the sample, per g, ml or cm². (using counts unit)

% of values below LOQ:% of values used for mean calculation below LOQ

Standard deviation: standard deviation of the concentration of the hazards in the sample, per g, ml or cm².

Automatic calculation (from mean and standard deviation), not relevant to PIF.

Confidence interval of the mean at 95%

- **Value lower bound**

- N=sample size
- sd=standard deviation
- $Mean - 1.96 \frac{sd}{\sqrt{N}}$

- **Value upper bound**

- $Mean + 1.96 \frac{sd}{\sqrt{N}}$

Standard error: value or NA ⁷

Median: value

Pathogenicity

Total number of samples examined for pathogenicity determination: it is the total samples used in the pathogenicity assay by type of marker

Origin of the sample for pathogenicity determination: samples positive using detection method, samples positive using enumeration method, samples positive for detection and enumeration, other (explain if other free text)

Type of marker: TDH only/TRH only/both/other
Other: precise

Pathogenic (%): Number of samples with potentially pathogenic isolates in the samples tested by type of marker.

Comments: if any

Strain characterisation/identification:

Number of samples for identification: samples that have been analysed for identification of the pathogen

Origin of samples for identification: samples positive using detection method, samples positive using enumeration method, samples positive for detection and enumeration, other

Comments: if any: extrapolation from publication, by example

Bias potential : if bias =1 existing potential for bias

BiasType: select among the classes: Aggregation bias, Reporting bias, Detection bias, Quality of reporting, Multiple, Other.

Reason bias: explain all bias with value 1.

⁷ Will be done in excel FILE, see later if relevant to be introduced in PIF database

The eligible articles will be divided by two, so that the two trained reviewers will collect the data independently. At the end, one reviewer will verify the conformity of the data extracted by the other. Any doubts will be solved with the senior reviewer(s) in bimonthly meetings.

3. Maintenance of the Reference Databases

For each SR process, three reference databases will be kept and duly uploaded on the Zenodo Community “Resources of PIF” (<https://zenodo.org/communities/pif>) at the end of every search-insertion period. BibTeX filenames will have the following format (Annex 2):

XYPeriod_WithoutDups.BibTeX: de-duplicated records of studies published in the period X to Y.

XYPeriod_Clean.BibTeX: eligible records of studies ready for insertion in the PIF database, published in the period X to Y.

XYPeriod_CleanFinal.BibTeX: final records whose data were inserted on PIF database, covering studies published in the period X to Y.

4. Modifications to the protocol

Any modification to the present protocol during the implementation of the project will be agreed upon between the parties and will be made effective through written amendment.

5. Bibliography

FDA-BAM. 2004. Bacteriological analytical manual chapter 9: *Vibrio*. Food & Drug Administration, Bacteriological Analytical Manual, U.S. Department of health and Human Services, Public Health Service, Washington DC. <https://www.fda.gov/food/foodscienceresearch/laboratorymethods/ucm070830.htm>

NMKL method N°156, 2nd ed. 1997. Pathogenic *Vibrio* species. Detection and enumeration in foods

MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Health Products and Food Branch, Government of Canada). Part 1: Detection of halophilic *Vibrio* species in seafood; Part 2: Detection of *Vibrio cholerae*.

6. Funding

This research is funded by EFSA through a grant agreement (GP/EFSA/BIOHAW/2023/05; 1 September 2023 – 31 August 2026).

7. Disclaimer

EFSA is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information in this protocol.

8. Annexes

Annex 1: Search strategies

Description: Search strategies for retrieving records from four bibliographic databases for systematic reviews linked to the PIF database

Web of Science

TS=(“microbial quality” OR “microbial safety” OR “microbiological quality” OR “microbiological safety” OR analyses OR analysis OR concentration OR contamination OR count* OR detection OR enumeration OR incidence OR investigation OR occurrence OR presence OR prevalence OR sampling OR survey*)

AND

TS=(“Vibrio parahaemolyticus” OR “Vibrio vulnificus” OR “V parahaemolyticus” OR “V vulnificus” OR ((Vibrio OR cholerae) NEAR/3 (non-O1 OR non-O139 OR nonO1 OR nonO139 OR non-01 OR non-0139 OR non01 OR non0139)))

AND

TS=(seafood OR seafoods OR “sea food” OR “sea foods” OR crustacean* OR shellfish OR bivalve* OR mollusc* OR mollusk* OR fish* OR finfish OR “fishery product*” OR “marine gasteropod*” OR cephalopod OR cephalopods OR crustacean OR crustaceans OR echinoderm OR echinoderms OR “sea urchin” OR “sea urchins” OR holoturid* OR tunicate OR tunicates OR urchin* OR crab* OR prawn* OR shrimp* OR lobster* OR “crayfish” OR crabfish OR crawfish OR langoustine OR scampi OR “clam” OR “clams” OR “carpet shell*” OR scallop* OR Pecten OR oyster* OR cockle OR cockles OR mussel OR mussels OR mytilus OR “Pen shell*” OR snail* OR abalone* OR Nassarius OR “whelk*” OR Bolinus OR “murex” OR ormer OR Haliotis OR “true limpet*” OR Patella OR Cellana OR Buccinum OR Concholepas OR conch* OR winkle* OR periwinkle* OR octopus OR squid* OR cuttlefish OR nautilus* OR Todarodes OR Loligo OR Sepia OR Paracentrotus OR Strongylocentrotus OR “Echinus esculentus” OR “sea cucumber*” OR “cukes” OR piure* OR pyura OR “sea violet*” OR “sea tulip*” OR “sea peach*” OR “sea pineapple*” OR “ice floe” OR “sea squirt*” OR gravad OR graved OR "gravad lax" OR gravlax OR sushi OR sashimi OR surimi OR ceviche OR caviar OR albacore OR amberjack OR anchovy OR anchovies OR angler OR anglerfish* OR Anguilla OR argentine OR Argyrosomus OR bacha OR barbel OR barracuda OR basa OR bass OR beluga OR bib OR bigeye OR blackfish OR bleak OR blenny OR bluefish OR “blue runner” OR “blue shark” OR bonito OR branzino OR bream OR brill OR burbot OR butterfish OR Capellin OR carp OR catfish OR catshark OR

“Chelon auratus” OR chub OR “clupea harengus” OR cod OR comber OR conger OR corb OR cutlassfish OR cyclopterus OR Cyprinus OR cyprinidae OR dab OR “danubian wels” OR dentex OR dicentrarchus OR dogfish OR eel OR emperor OR engraulis OR flathead OR flounder OR “flying fish” OR forkbeard OR gadus OR garfish OR garrick OR goby OR goldline OR grouper OR guitarfish OR gunard OR haddock OR hake OR halibut OR hammerhead OR herring OR hippoglossus OR hoki OR huss OR icefish OR “John dory” OR “Katsuwonus pelamis” OR labrus OR lamprey OR lanternfish OR leerfish OR ling OR “little tunny” OR “Liza aurata” OR lophius OR lumpfish OR lythe OR mackerel OR “mahi mahi” OR “mallotus villosus” OR marlin OR meagre OR megrim OR melva OR merluccius OR Micromesistius OR monkfish OR moonfish OR mugil OR mullet OR “mullus barbatus” OR needlefish OR Oncorhynchus OR oreo OR osmeridae OR pacu OR pandoras OR panga OR pangasius OR parrotfish OR “parrot fish” OR perch OR picarel OR pike OR pikeperch OR pilchard OR pilotfish OR “pilot fish” OR platicthys OR plaice OR pleuronectes OR pollan OR Pollack OR Pollock OR ponyfish OR porbeagle OR pout OR pouting OR ray OR ribbonfish OR rigg OR rockfish OR rosefish OR sablefish OR sailfish OR salmon OR salmo OR sandeel OR sardine OR sardina OR sardinella OR scabbardfish OR scomber OR scophthalmus OR scorpionfish OR “sea bass” OR seabass OR seabream OR “sea bream” OR seriola OR sheatfish OR “shi drum” OR sild OR sillago OR skipjack OR smelt OR smooth hound OR “smooth-hound” OR snapper OR snook OR sole OR solea OR sparidae OR sparus OR sparring OR spearfish OR sprat OR sprattus OR “St Peter’s fish” OR stargazer OR stingray OR stizostedion OR sturgeon OR “surgeon fish” OR trachurus OR swordfish OR tailor OR tench OR theragra OR thunnus OR tilapia OR tinca OR threadfin OR triggerfish OR trisopterus OR trout OR tubefish OR tuna OR turbot OR tusk OR walleye OR weever OR whitebait OR whiting OR wrasse OR yellowtail meal OR meals OR food OR foods OR “buffet meal*” OR “complex food” OR “frozen meal*” OR multi-ingredient OR “multi ingredient” OR ready-to-eat OR RTE OR “ready meal” OR “ready prepared” OR “ready to eat” OR "under vacuum" OR composite* OR convenience OR cured OR dip OR dips OR dish OR dishes OR dressing* OR dumpling* OR fermented OR filling OR gravy OR macerated OR marinad* OR marinate* OR mayonnaise OR pasta OR pizza OR pickled OR preserved OR pudding* OR puree* OR salsa OR salsas OR salted OR sandwich* OR sashimi OR ceviche OR sauce* OR smoked OR snack OR snacks OR soup OR soups OR stew* OR surimi OR sushi OR topping* OR chowder)

AND

(AD=(Albania OR Andorra OR Armenia OR Austria OR Azerbaijan OR Belarus OR Belgium OR Bosnia and Herzegovina OR Bulgaria OR Croatia OR Cyprus OR Czech Republic OR Denmark OR England OR Estonia OR Finland OR France OR Georgia OR Germany OR Greece OR Hungary OR Iceland OR Ireland OR Italy OR Kazakhstan OR Kosovo OR Latvia OR Liechtenstein OR Lithuania OR Luxembourg OR Macedonia OR Malta OR Moldova OR Monaco OR Montenegro OR Netherlands OR North Macedonia OR Norway OR Poland OR Portugal OR Romania OR Russia OR San Marino OR Serbia OR Slovakia OR Slovenia OR Scotland OR Spain

OR Sweden OR Switzerland OR Turkey OR Türkiye OR Ukraine OR United Kingdom OR UK
OR Vatican OR Wales OR Yugoslavia OR Europe* OR EU OR Faroe*)
OR

TS=(Albania OR Andorra OR Armenia OR Austria OR Azerbaijan OR Belarus OR Belgium OR
Bosnia and Herzegovina OR Bulgaria OR Croatia OR Cyprus OR Czech Republic OR Denmark
OR England OR Estonia OR Finland OR France OR Georgia OR Germany OR Greece OR
Hungary OR Iceland OR Ireland OR Italy OR Kazakhstan OR Kosovo OR Latvia OR
Liechtenstein OR Lithuania OR Luxembourg OR Macedonia OR Malta OR Moldova OR Monaco
OR Montenegro OR Netherlands OR North Macedonia OR Norway OR Poland OR Portugal OR
Romania OR Russia OR San Marino OR Serbia OR Slovakia OR Slovenia OR Scotland OR Spain
OR Sweden OR Switzerland OR Turkey OR Türkiye OR Ukraine OR United Kingdom OR UK
OR Vatican OR Wales OR Yugoslavia OR Europe* OR EU OR Faroe*))

NOT

(TS= (“*in vitro*” OR “*in-vitro*” OR “challenge study” OR “essential oil*” OR attribution OR
biofilm* OR “plant extract” OR “extracts” OR feed OR livestock OR sanitiser OR sanitizer OR
spiked OR “feed supplement*”))

PubMed

(“microbial quality”[tiab] OR “microbial safety”[tiab] OR “microbiological quality”[tiab] OR
“microbiological safety”[tiab] OR analyses[tiab] OR analysis[tiab] OR concentration[tiab] OR
contamination[tiab] OR count*[tiab] OR detection[tiab] OR enumeration[tiab] OR
incidence[tiab] OR investigation[tiab] OR occurrence[tiab] OR presence[tiab] OR
prevalence[tiab] OR sampling[tiab] OR survey*[tiab])

AND

(“*Vibrio parahaemolyticus*” [tiab] OR “*V. parahaemolyticus*”[tiab] OR “*Vibrio vulnificus*” [tiab]
OR “*V. vulnificus*”[tiab] OR (“*Vibrio cholerae*” [tiab] OR “*V. cholerae*” [tiab]) AND (“non-
O1” [tiab] OR “non-O139” [tiab] OR “nonO1” [tiab] OR “nonO139” [tiab] OR “non-O1” [tiab]
OR “non-O139” [tiab] OR “nonO1” [tiab] OR “nonO139” [tiab]))

AND

(seafood[tiab] OR seafoods[tiab] OR "sea food"[tiab] OR "sea foods"[tiab] OR crustacean*[tiab]
OR shellfish[tiab] OR bivalve*[tiab] OR mollusc*[tiab] OR mollusk*[tiab] OR fish*[tiab] OR
finfish[tiab] OR "fishery product*" [tiab] OR "marine gasteropod*" [tiab] OR cephalopod[tiab]
OR cephalopods[tiab] OR crustacean[tiab] OR crustaceans[tiab] OR echinoderm[tiab] OR
echinoderms[tiab] OR "sea urchin"[tiab] OR "sea urchins"[tiab] OR holoturid*[tiab] OR

tunicate[tiab] OR tunicates[tiab] OR urchin*[tiab] OR crab*[tiab] OR prawn*[tiab] OR shrimp*[tiab] OR lobster*[tiab] OR "crayfish"[tiab] OR crabfish[tiab] OR crawfish[tiab] OR langoustine[tiab] OR scampi[tiab] OR clam[tiab] OR clams[tiab] OR "carpet shell"[tiab] OR scallop*[tiab] OR Pecten[tiab] OR oyster*[tiab] OR cockle[tiab] OR cockles[tiab] OR mussel[tiab] OR mussels[tiab] OR mytilus[tiab] OR "Pen shell"[tiab] OR snail*[tiab] OR abalone*[tiab] OR Nassarius[tiab] OR "whelk"[tiab] OR Bolinus[tiab] OR murex[tiab] OR ormer[tiab] OR Haliotis[tiab] OR "true limpet"[tiab] OR Patella[tiab] OR Cellana[tiab] OR Buccinum[tiab] OR Concholepas[tiab] OR conch*[tiab] OR winkle*[tiab] OR periwinkle*[tiab] OR octopus*[tiab] OR squid*[tiab] OR cuttlefish*[tiab] OR nautilus*[tiab] OR Todarodes[tiab] OR Loligo[tiab] OR Sepia*[tiab] OR Paracentrotus[tiab] OR Strongylocentrotus[tiab] OR "Echinus esculentus"[tiab] OR "sea cucumber"[tiab] OR "cukes"[tiab] OR piure*[tiab] OR pyura[tiab] OR "sea violet"[tiab] OR "sea tulip"[tiab] OR "sea peach"[tiab] OR "sea pineapple"[tiab] OR "ice floe"[tiab] OR "sea squirt"[tiab] OR gravad [tiab] OR gravad[tiab] OR "gravad lax"[tiab] OR gravlax[tiab] OR sushi[tiab] OR sashimi[tiab] OR surimi[tiab] OR ceviche[tiab] OR caviar[tiab] OR albacore[tiab] OR amberjack*[tiab] OR anchovy[tiab] OR anchovies[tiab] OR angler[tiab] OR anglerfish*[tiab] OR anguilla*[tiab] OR argentine[tiab] OR Argyrosomus[tiab] OR bacha[tiab] OR barbel[tiab] OR barbels[tiab] OR barracuda*[tiab] OR basa[tiab] OR bass[tiab] OR beluga[tiab] OR bib[tiab] OR bigeye[tiab] OR blackfish*[tiab] OR bleak[tiab] OR blenny[tiab] OR bluefish*[tiab] OR "blue runner"[tiab] OR "blue shark"[tiab] OR bonito*[tiab] OR branzino*[tiab] OR bream[tiab] OR breams[tiab] OR brill[tiab] OR burbot*[tiab] OR butterfish*[tiab] OR Capellin[tiab] OR carp[tiab] OR carps[tiab] OR catfish*[tiab] OR catshark*[tiab] OR "Chelon auratus"[tiab] OR chub[tiab] OR "clupea harengus"[tiab] OR cod[tiab] OR comber[tiab] OR conger[tiab] OR corb[tiab] OR cutlassfish[tiab] OR cyclopterus[tiab] OR Cyprinus[tiab] OR cyprinidae[tiab] OR dab[tiab] OR "danubian wels"[tiab] OR dentex[tiab] OR dicentrarchus[tiab] OR dogfish[tiab] OR eel[tiab] OR emperor[tiab] OR engraulis[tiab] OR flathead[tiab] OR flounder[tiab] OR "flying fish"[tiab] OR forkbeard[tiab] OR gadus[tiab] OR garfish[tiab] OR garrick[tiab] OR goby[tiab] OR goldline[tiab] OR grouper[tiab] OR guitarfish[tiab] OR gunard[tiab] OR haddock[tiab] OR hake[tiab] OR halibut[tiab] OR hammerhead[tiab] OR herring[tiab] OR hippoglossus[tiab] OR hoki[tiab] OR huss[tiab] OR icefish[tiab] OR "John dory"[tiab] OR "Katsuwonus pelamis" OR labrus[tiab] OR lamprey[tiab] OR lanternfish[tiab] OR leerfish[tiab] OR ling[tiab] OR "little tunny"[tiab] OR "Liza aurata" OR lophius[tiab] OR lumpfish[tiab] OR lythe[tiab] OR mackerel[tiab] OR "mahi mahi"[tiab] OR "mallotus villosus"[tiab] OR marlin[tiab] OR meagre[tiab] OR megrim[tiab] OR melva[tiab] OR merluccius[tiab] OR Micromesistius[tiab] OR monkfish[tiab] OR moonfish[tiab] OR mugil[tiab] OR mullet[tiab] OR "mullus barbatus"[tiab] OR needlefish[tiab] OR Oncorhynchus[tiab] OR oreo[tiab] OR osmeridae[tiab] OR pacu[tiab] OR pandoras[tiab] OR panga[tiab] OR pangasius[tiab] OR parrotfish[tiab] OR "parrot fish"[tiab] OR perch[tiab] OR picarel[tiab] OR pike[tiab] OR pikeperch[tiab] OR pilchard[tiab] OR pilotfish[tiab] OR "pilot fish"[tiab] OR platichthys[tiab] OR plaice[tiab] OR pleuronectes[tiab] OR pollan[tiab] OR Pollack[tiab] OR Pollock[tiab] OR ponyfish[tiab] OR porbeagle[tiab] OR pout[tiab] OR pouting[tiab] OR ray[tiab] OR ribbonfish[tiab] OR rigg[tiab] OR rockfish[tiab] OR rosefish[tiab] OR sablefish[tiab] OR sailfish[tiab] OR salmon[tiab] OR salmo[tiab] OR

sandeel[tiab] OR sardine[tiab] OR sardina[tiab] OR sardinella[tiab] OR scabbardfish[tiab] OR scomber[tiab] OR scophthalmus[tiab] OR scorpionfish[tiab] OR "sea bass"OR seabass[tiab] OR seabream[tiab] OR "sea bream"[tiab] OR seriola[tiab] OR sheatfish[tiab] OR "shi drum"[tiab] OR sild[tiab] OR sillago[tiab] OR skipjack[tiab] OR smelt[tiab] OR smooth hound[tiab] OR "smooth-hound"[tiab] OR snapper[tiab] OR snook[tiab] OR sole[tiab] OR solea[tiab] OR sparidae[tiab] OR sparus[tiab] OR sparring[tiab] OR spearfish[tiab] OR sprat[tiab] OR sprattus[tiab] OR "St Peter's fish"[tiab] OR stargazer[tiab] OR stingray[tiab] OR stizostedion[tiab] OR sturgeon[tiab] OR "surgeon fish"[tiab] OR trachurus[tiab] OR swordfish[tiab] OR tailor[tiab] OR tench[tiab] OR theragra[tiab] OR thunnus[tiab] OR tilapia[tiab] OR tinca[tiab] OR threadfin[tiab] OR triggerfish[tiab] OR trisopterus[tiab] OR trout[tiab] OR tubefish[tiab] OR tuna[tiab] OR turbot[tiab] OR tusk[tiab] OR walleye[tiab] OR weever[tiab] OR whitebait[tiab] OR whiting[tiab] OR wrasse[tiab] OR yellowtail[tiab] OR meal[tiab] OR meals[tiab] OR food[tiab] OR foods[tiab] OR "buffet meal*" [tiab] OR "complex food"[tiab] OR "frozen meal*" [tiab] OR multi-ingredient[tiab] OR "multi ingredient"[tiab] OR ready-to-eat[tiab] OR RTE[tiab] OR "ready meal"[tiab] OR "ready prepared"[tiab] OR "ready to eat"[tiab] OR "under vacuum"[tiab] OR composite*[tiab] OR convenience[tiab] OR cured[tiab] OR dip[tiab] OR dips[tiab] OR dish[tiab] OR dishes[tiab] OR dressing*[tiab] OR dumpling*[tiab] OR fermented[tiab] OR filling[tiab] OR gravy[tiab] OR macerated[tiab] OR marinad*[tiab] OR marinate*[tiab] OR mayonnaise[tiab] OR pasta[tiab] OR pizza[tiab] OR pickled[tiab] OR preserved[tiab] OR pudding*[tiab] OR puree*[tiab] OR salsa[tiab] OR salsas[tiab] OR salted[tiab] OR sandwich*[tiab] OR sashimi[tiab] OR ceviche[tiab] OR sauce*[tiab] OR smoked[tiab] OR snack[tiab] OR snacks[tiab] OR soup[tiab] OR soups[tiab] OR stew*[tiab] OR surimi[tiab] OR sushi[tiab] OR topping*[tiab] OR (chowder[tiab])

NOT ("in vitro"[tiab] OR "in-vitro"[tiab] OR "challenge study"[tiab] OR "essential oil*" [tiab] OR attribution[tiab] OR biofilm*[tiab] OR "plant extract"[tiab] OR "extracts"[tiab] OR feed[tiab] OR livestock[tiab] OR sanitiser[tiab] OR sanitizer[tiab] OR spiked[tiab] OR "feed supplement*" [tiab])

AND

((Albania[ad] OR Andorra[ad] OR Armenia[ad] OR Austria[ad] OR Azerbaijan[ad] OR Belarus[ad] OR Belgium[ad] OR Bosnia and Herzegovina[ad] OR Bulgaria[ad] OR Croatia[ad] OR Cyprus[ad] OR Czech Republic[ad] OR Denmark[ad] OR England[ad] OR Estonia[ad] OR Finland[ad] OR France[ad] OR Georgia[ad] OR Germany[ad] OR Greece[ad] OR Hungary[ad] OR Iceland[ad] OR Ireland[ad] OR Italy[ad] OR Kazakhstan[ad] OR Kosovo[ad] OR Latvia[ad] OR Liechtenstein[ad] OR Lithuania[ad] OR Luxembourg[ad] OR Macedonia[ad] OR Malta[ad] OR Moldova[ad] OR Monaco[ad] OR Montenegro[ad] OR Netherlands[ad] OR North Macedonia[ad] OR Norway[ad] OR Poland[ad] OR Portugal[ad] OR Romania[ad] OR Russia[ad] OR San Marino[ad] OR Serbia[ad] OR Slovakia[ad] OR Slovenia[ad] OR Scotland[ad] OR Spain[ad] OR Sweden[ad] OR Switzerland[ad] OR Turkey[ad] OR Türkiye[ad] OR Ukraine[ad])

OR United Kingdom[ad] OR UK[ad] OR Vatican[ad] OR Wales[ad] OR Yugoslavia[ad] OR Europe*[ad] OR EU[ad] OR Faroe[ad] OR Faroes[ad])

OR

(Albania[tiab] OR Andorra[tiab] OR Armenia[tiab] OR Austria[tiab] OR Azerbaijan[tiab] OR Belarus[tiab] OR Belgium[tiab] OR Bosnia and Herzegovina[tiab] OR Bulgaria[tiab] OR Croatia[tiab] OR Cyprus[tiab] OR Czech Republic[tiab] OR Denmark[tiab] OR England[tiab] OR Estonia[tiab] OR Finland[tiab] OR France[tiab] OR Georgia[tiab] OR Germany[tiab] OR Greece[tiab] OR Hungary[tiab] OR Iceland[tiab] OR Ireland[tiab] OR Italy[tiab] OR Kazakhstan[tiab] OR Kosovo[tiab] OR Latvia[tiab] OR Liechtenstein[tiab] OR Lithuania[tiab] OR Luxembourg[tiab] OR Macedonia[tiab] OR Malta[tiab] OR Moldova[tiab] OR Monaco[tiab] OR Montenegro[tiab] OR Netherlands[tiab] OR North Macedonia[tiab] OR Norway[tiab] OR Poland[tiab] OR Portugal[tiab] OR Romania[tiab] OR Russia[tiab] OR San Marino[tiab] OR Serbia[tiab] OR Slovakia[tiab] OR Slovenia[tiab] OR Scotland[tiab] OR Spain[tiab] OR Sweden[tiab] OR Switzerland[tiab] OR Turkey[tiab] OR Türkiye[tiab] OR Ukraine[tiab] OR United Kingdom[tiab] OR UK[tiab] OR Vatican[tiab] OR Wales[tiab] OR Yugoslavia[tiab] OR Europe*[tiab] OR EU[tiab] OR Faroe[tiab] OR Faroes[tiab])

OR

(Albania[mh] OR Andorra[mh] OR Armenia[mh] OR Austria[mh] OR Azerbaijan[mh] OR Belarus[mh] OR Belgium[mh] OR Bosnia and Herzegovina[mh] OR Bulgaria[mh] OR Croatia[mh] OR Cyprus[mh] OR Czech Republic[mh] OR Denmark[mh] OR England[mh] OR Estonia[mh] OR Finland[mh] OR France[mh] OR Georgia[mh] OR Germany[mh] OR Greece[mh] OR Hungary[mh] OR Iceland[mh] OR Ireland[mh] OR Italy[mh] OR Kazakhstan[mh] OR Kosovo[mh] OR Latvia[mh] OR Liechtenstein[mh] OR Lithuania[mh] OR Luxembourg[mh] OR Macedonia[mh] OR Malta[mh] OR Moldova[mh] OR Monaco[mh] OR Montenegro[mh] OR Netherlands[mh] OR North Macedonia[mh] OR Norway[mh] OR Poland[mh] OR Portugal[mh] OR Romania[mh] OR Russia[mh] OR San Marino[mh] OR Serbia[mh] OR Slovakia[mh] OR Slovenia[mh] OR Scotland[mh] OR Spain[mh] OR Sweden[mh] OR Switzerland[mh] OR Turkey[mh] OR Türkiye[mh] OR Ukraine[mh] OR United Kingdom[mh] OR "Vatican City"[mh] OR Wales[mh] OR Yugoslavia[mh] OR Europe[mh] OR "European Union"[Mesh] OR Faroe and islands[mh]))

Scopus

(TITLE-ABS-KEY("microbial quality") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("microbial safety") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("microbiological quality") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("microbiological safety") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(analysis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(analysis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(concentration) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(contamination) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(count*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(detection) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(enumeration) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(incidence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(investigation) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(occurrence) OR

TITLE-ABS-KEY(presence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(prevalence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sampling) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(survey*))

AND

(TITLE-ABS-KEY("Vibrio parahaemolyticus") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("Vibrio vulnificus") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("parahaemolyticus") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("vulnificus") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY((vibrio OR cholerae) PRE/3 (non-O1 OR non-O139 OR nonO1 OR nonO139 OR non-01 OR non-0139 OR nonO1 OR nonO139)))

AND

(TITLE-ABS-KEY(seafood) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(seafoods) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("sea food") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("sea foods") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(crustacean*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(shellfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bivalve*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mollusc*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mollusk*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(fish*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(finfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("fishery product*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("marine gasteropod*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cephalopod) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cephalopods) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(crustacean) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(crustaceans) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(echinoderm) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(echinoderms) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("sea urchin") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("sea urchins") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(holoturid*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tunicate) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tunicates) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(urchin*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(crab*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(prawn*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(shrimp*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(lobster*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("crayfish") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(crabfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(crawfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(langoustine) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(scampi) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("clam") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("clams") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("carpet shell*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(scallop*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Pecten) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(oyster*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cockle) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cockles) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mussel) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mussels) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mytilus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("Pen shell*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(snail*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(abalone*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Nassarius) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("whelk*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Bolinus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("murex") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY() OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mer) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Haliotis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("true limpet*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Patella) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Cellana) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Buccinum) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Concholepas) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(conch*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(winkle*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(periwinkle*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(octopus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(squid*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cuttlefish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(nautilus*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Todarodes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Loligo) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Sepia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Paracentrotus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Strongylocentrotus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(

“Echinus esculentus”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“sea cucumber*”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“cukes”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(piure*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pyura) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“sea violet*”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“sea tulip*”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“sea peach*”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“sea pineapple*”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“ice floe”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“sea squirt*”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(gravad) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(graved) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("gravad lax") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(gravlax) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sush) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sashimi) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(surimi) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ceviche) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(caviar) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(albacore) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(amberjack) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(anchovy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(anchovies) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(angler OR anglerfish*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY([anguilla](#)) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(argentine) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Argyrosomus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bacha) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(barbel) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(barracuda) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(basa) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bass) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(beluga) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bib) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bigeye) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(blackfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bleak) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(blenny) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bluefish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“blue runner”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“blue shark”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bonito) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(branzino) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(bream) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(brill) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(burbot) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(butterfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Capellin) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(carp) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(catfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(catshark) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“Chelon auratus”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(chub) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“clupea harengus”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cod) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(comber) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(conger) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(corb) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cutlassfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cyclopterus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Cyprinus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cyprinidae) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dab) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“danubian wels”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dentex) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dicentrarchus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dogfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(eel) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(emperor) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(engraulis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(flathead) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(flounder) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“flying fish”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(forkbeard) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(gadus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(garfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(garrick) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(goby) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(goldline) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(grouper) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(guitarfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(gunard) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(haddock) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hake) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(halibut) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hammerhead) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(herring) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hippoglossus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hoki) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(huss) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(icefish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“John dory”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“Katsuwonus pelamis”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(labrus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(lamprey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(lanternfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(leerfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ling) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“little tunny”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“Liza aurata”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(lophius) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(lumpfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(lythe) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mackerel) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“mahi mahi”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(“mallotus villosus”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(marlin) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(meagre) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(megrim) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(melva) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(merluccius) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Micromesistius) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(monkfish)

OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(moonfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mugil) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mullet) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("mullus barbatus") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(needlefish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Oncorhynchus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(oreo) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(osmeridae) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pacu) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pandoras) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(panga) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pangasius) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(parrotfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("parrot fish") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(perch) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(picarel) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pike) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pikeperch) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pilchard) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pilotfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("pilot fish") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(platicthys) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(plaice) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pleuronectes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pollan) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Pollack) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Pollock) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ponyfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(porbeagle) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pout) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pouting) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ray) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ribbonfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(rigg) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(rockfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(rosefish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sablefish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sailfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salmon) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salmo) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sandeel) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sardine) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sardina) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sardinella) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(scabbardfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(scomber) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(scophthalmus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(scorpionfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("sea bass") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(seabass) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(seabream) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("sea bream") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(seriola) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sheatfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("shi drum") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sild) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sillago) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(skipjack) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(smelt) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(smooth hound) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("smooth-hound") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(snapper) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(snook) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sole) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(solea) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sparidae) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sparus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sparling) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(spearfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sprat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sprattus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("St Peter's fish") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(stargazer) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(stingray) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(stizostedion) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sturgeon) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("surgeon fish") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(trachurus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(swordfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tailor) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tench) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(theragra) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(thunnus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tilapia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tinca) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(threadfin) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(triggerfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(trisopterus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(trout) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tubefish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tuna) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(turbot) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tusk) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(walleye) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(weever) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(whitebait) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(whiting) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(wrasse) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(yellowtail) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(meal) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(meals) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(food) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(foods) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("buffet meal*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("complex food") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("frozen meal*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(multi-ingredient) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("multi ingredient") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ready-to-eat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(RTE) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("ready meal") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("ready prepared") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("ready to eat") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY("under

vacuum") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(composite*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(convenience) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(cured) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dip) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dips) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dishes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dressing*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(dumpling*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(fermented) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(filling) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(gravy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(macerated) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(marinad*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(marinate*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(mayonnaise) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pasta) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pizza) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pickled) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(preserved) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(pudding*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(puree*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salsa) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salsas) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(salted) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sandwich*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sashimi) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(ceviche) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sauce*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(smoked) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(snack) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(snacks) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(soup) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(soups) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(stew*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(surimi) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sushi) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(topping*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(chowder))

AND

((AFFIL(Albania) OR AFFIL(Andorra) OR AFFIL(Armenia) OR AFFIL(Austria) OR AFFIL(Azerbaijan) OR AFFIL(Belarus) OR AFFIL(Belgium) OR AFFIL(Bosnia and Herzegovina) OR AFFIL(Bulgaria) OR AFFIL(Croatia) OR AFFIL(Cyprus) OR AFFIL(Czech Republic) OR AFFIL(Denmark) OR AFFIL(England) OR AFFIL(Estonia) OR AFFIL(Finland) OR AFFIL(France) OR AFFIL(Georgia) OR AFFIL(Germany) OR AFFIL(Greece) OR AFFIL(Hungary) OR AFFIL(Iceland) OR AFFIL(Ireland) OR AFFIL(Italy) OR AFFIL(Kazakhstan) OR AFFIL(Kosovo) OR AFFIL(Latvia) OR AFFIL(Liechtenstein) OR AFFIL(Lithuania) OR AFFIL(Luxembourg) OR AFFIL(Macedonia) OR AFFIL(Malta) OR AFFIL(Moldova) OR AFFIL(Monaco) OR AFFIL(Montenegro) OR AFFIL(Netherlands) OR AFFIL(North Macedonia) OR AFFIL(Norway) OR AFFIL(Poland) OR AFFIL(Portugal) OR AFFIL(Romania) OR AFFIL(Russia) OR AFFIL(San Marino) OR AFFIL(Serbia) OR AFFIL(Slovakia) OR AFFIL(Slovenia) OR AFFIL(Scotland) OR AFFIL(Spain) OR AFFIL(Sweden) OR AFFIL(Switzerland) OR AFFIL(Turkey) OR AFFIL(Türkiye) OR AFFIL(Ukraine) OR AFFIL(United Kingdom) OR AFFIL(UK) OR AFFIL(Vatican) OR AFFIL(Wales) OR AFFIL(Yugoslavia) OR AFFIL(Europe*) OR AFFIL(EU) OR AFFIL(Faroe*))

OR

(TITLE-ABS-KEY(Albania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Andorra) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Armenia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Austria) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Azerbaijan) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Belarus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Belgium) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Bosnia and Herzegovina) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Bulgaria) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Croatia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Cyprus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Czech Republic) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Denmark) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(England) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Estonia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Finland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(France) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Georgia) OR TITLE-ABS-

KEY(Germany) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Greece) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Hungary) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Iceland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Ireland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Italy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Kazakhstan) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Kosovo) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Latvia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Liechtenstein) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Lithuania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Luxembourg) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Macedonia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Malta) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Moldova) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Monaco) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Montenegro) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Netherlands) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(North Macedonia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Norway) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Poland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Portugal) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Romania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Russia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(San Marino) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Serbia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Slovakia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Slovenia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Scotland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Spain) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Sweden) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Switzerland) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Turkey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Türkiye) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Ukraine) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(United Kingdom) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(UK) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Vatican) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Wales) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Yugoslavia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(EU) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(Faroe*))

AND NOT

(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("in vitro") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("in-vitro") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("challenge study") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("essential oil*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (attribution) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (biofilm*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("plant extract") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("extracts") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (feed) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (livestock) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sanitiser) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sanitizer) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (spiked) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("feed supplement*"))

Filter mechanisms to be applied:

i. Type of publication (primary research articles, reviews, undefined)

Filter by document types ‘Article’, ‘Review’

[or in the query string, add: AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re")]

ii. Language (English, Spanish, French, Portuguese, undefined)

AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"French") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"Spanish") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"Portuguese") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"Undefined") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"German") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"Italian"))]

SciELO

Common to all search:

((“microbial quality”) OR (“microbial safety”) OR (“microbiological quality”) OR (“microbiological safety”) OR (analyses) OR (analysis) OR (concentration) OR (contamination) OR (count*) OR (detection) OR (enumeration) OR (incidence) OR (investigation) OR (occurrence) OR (presence) OR (prevalence) OR (sampling) OR (survey*))

AND (“Vibrio parahaemolyticus”) OR (V. parahaemolyticus) OR (“Vibrio vulnificus”) OR (“V. vulnificus”) OR (((“Vibrio cholerae”) OR (“V. cholerae”)) AND ((“non-O1”) OR (“non-O139”) OR (“nonO1”) OR (“nonO139”) OR (“non-01”) OR (“non-0139”) OR (“nonO1”) OR (“nonO139”))))

AND NOT

((“in vitro”) OR (“in-vitro”) OR (“challenge study”) OR (“essential oil*”) OR (antimicrobial*) OR (attribution) OR (biofilm*) OR (“plant extract”) OR (“extracts”) OR (feed) OR (livestock) OR (sanitiser) OR (sanitizer) OR (spiked) OR (“feed supplement*”))

AND

Search 1

((seafood) OR (seafoods) OR (“sea food”) OR (“sea foods”) OR (crustacean*) OR (shellfish) OR (bivalve*) OR (mollusc*) OR (mollusk*) OR (fish*) OR (finfish) OR (“fishery product*”) OR (“marine gasteropod*”) OR (cephalopod) OR (cephalopods) OR (crustacean) OR (crustaceans) OR (echinoderm) OR (echinoderms) OR (“sea urchin”) OR (“sea urchins”) OR (holoturid*) OR (tunicate) OR (tunicates) OR (urchin*) OR (crab*) OR (prawn*) OR (shrimp*) OR (lobster*) OR (“crayfish”) OR (crabfish) OR (crawfish) OR (langoustine) OR (scampi) OR (“clam”) OR (“clams”) OR (“carpet shell*”) OR (scallop*) OR (Pecten) OR (oyster*) OR (cockle) OR (cockles) OR (mussel) OR (mussels) OR (mytilus) OR (“Pen shell*”) OR (snail*) OR (abalone*) OR (Nassarius) OR (“whelk*”) OR (Bolinus) OR (“murex”) OR (ormer) OR (Haliotis) OR (“true limpet*”) OR (Patella) OR (Cellana) OR (Buccinum) OR (Concholepas) OR (conch*) OR (winkle*))

Search 2

((periwinkle*) OR (octopus) OR (squid*) OR (cuttlefish) OR (nautilus*) OR (Todarodes) OR (Loligo) OR (Sepia) OR (Paracentrotus) OR (Strongylocentrotus) OR (“Echinus esculentus”) OR (“sea cucumber*”) OR (“cukes”) OR (piure*) OR (pyura) OR (“sea violet*”) OR (“sea tulip*”) OR (“sea peach*”) OR (“sea pineapple*”) OR (“ice floe”) OR (“sea squirt*”) OR (gravad) OR (graved) OR (“gravad lax”) OR (gravlax) OR (sushi) OR (sashimi) OR (surimi) OR (ceviche) OR

(caviar) OR (albacore) OR (amberjack) OR (anchovy) OR (anchovies) OR (angler) OR (anglerfish*) OR (anguilla) OR (argentine) OR (Argyrosomus) OR (bacha) OR (barbel) OR (barracuda) OR (basa) OR (bass) OR (beluga) OR (bib) OR (bigeye) OR (blackfish) OR (bleak) OR (blenny) OR (bluefish) OR (“blue runner”) OR (“blue shark”) OR (bonito) OR (branzino) OR (bream) OR (brill) OR (burbot) OR (butterfish) OR (Capellin) OR (carp) OR (catfish) OR (catshark) OR (“Chelon auratus”) OR (chub) OR (“clupea harengus”) OR (cod) OR (comber) OR (conger) OR (corb) OR (cutlassfish) OR (cyclopterus) OR (Cyprinus) OR (cyprinidae) OR (dab) OR (“danubian wels”) OR (dentex) OR (dicentrarchus) OR (dogfish) OR (eel) OR (emperor) OR (engraulis) OR (flathead) OR (flounder) OR (“flying fish”) OR (forkbeard) OR (gadus) OR (garfish) OR (garrick) OR (goby) OR (goldline) OR (grouper) OR (guitarfish) OR (gunard) OR (haddock) OR (hake) OR (halibut) OR (hammerhead) OR (herring) OR (hippoglossus) OR (hoki) OR (huss) OR (icefish) OR (“John dory”) OR (“Katsuwonus pelamis”) OR (labrus) OR (lamprey) OR (lanternfish) OR (leerfish) OR (ling) OR (“little tunny”) OR (“Liza aurata”) OR (lophius) OR (lumpfish) OR (lythe) OR (mackerel) OR (“mahi mahi”) OR (“mallotus villosus”) OR (marlin) OR (meagre) OR (megrin))

Search 3

((melva) OR (merluccius) OR (Micromesistius) OR (monkfish) OR (moonfish) OR (mugil) OR (mullet) OR (“mullus barbatus”) OR (needlefish) OR (Oncorhynchus) OR (oreo) OR (osmeridae) OR (pacu) OR (pandoras) OR (panga) OR (pangasius) OR (parrotfish) OR (“parrot fish”) OR (perch) OR (picarel) OR (pike) OR (pikeperch) OR (pilchard) OR (pilotfish) OR (“pilot fish”) OR (platichthys) OR (plaice) OR (pleuronectes) OR (pollan) OR (Pollack) OR (Pollock) OR (ponyfish) OR (porbeagle) OR (pout) OR (pouting) OR (ray) OR (ribbonfish) OR (rigg) OR (rockfish) OR (rosefish) OR (sablefish) OR (sailfish) OR (salmon) OR (salmo) OR (sandeel) OR (sardine) OR (sardina) OR (sardinella) OR (scabbardfish) OR (scomber) OR (scophthalmus) OR (scorpionfish) OR (“sea bass”) OR (seabass) OR (seabream) OR (“sea bream”) OR (seriola) OR (sheatfish) OR (“shi drum”) OR (sild) OR (sillago) OR (skipjack) OR (smelt) OR (smooth hound) OR (“smooth-hound”) OR (snapper) OR (snook) OR (sole) OR (solea) OR (sparidae) OR (sparus) OR (sparling) OR (spearfish) OR (sprat) OR (sprattus) OR (“St Peter’s fish”) OR (stargazer) OR (stingray) OR (stizostedion) OR (sturgeon) OR (“surgeon fish”) OR (trachurus) OR (swordfish) OR (tailor) OR (tench) OR (theragra) OR (thunnus) OR (tilapia) OR (tinca) OR (threadfin) OR (triggerfish) OR (trisopterus) OR (trout) OR (tubefish) OR (tuna) OR (turbot) OR (tusk) OR (walleye) OR (weever) OR (whitebait) OR (whiting) OR (wrasse) OR (yellowtail))

Search 4

((meal) OR (meals) OR (food) OR (foods) OR (“buffet meal”) OR (“complex food”) OR (“frozen meal”) OR (multi-ingredient) OR (“multi ingredient”) OR (ready-to-eat) OR (RTE) OR (“ready meal”) OR (“ready prepared”) OR (“ready to eat”) OR (“under vacuum”) OR (composite*) OR (convenience) OR (cured) OR (dip) OR (dips) OR (dish) OR (dishes) OR (dressing*) OR (dumpling*) OR (fermented) OR (filling) OR (gravy) OR (macerated) OR (marinad*) OR (marinate*) OR (mayonnaise) OR (pasta) OR (pizza) OR (pickled) OR

(preserved) OR (pudding*) OR (puree*) OR (salsa) OR (salsas) OR (salted) OR (sandwich*) OR (sashimi) OR (ceviche) OR (sauce*) OR (smoked) OR (snack) OR (snacks) OR (soup) OR (soups) OR (stew*) OR (surimi) OR (sushi) OR (topping*)OR (chowder)

AND NOT

((“in vitro”) OR (“in-vitro”) OR (“challenge study”) OR (“essential oil*”) OR (attribution) OR (biofilm*) OR (“plant extract”) OR (“extracts”) OR (feed) OR (livestock) OR (sanitiser) OR (sanitizer) OR (spiked) OR (“feed supplement*”))

Annex 2: PRISMA chart template

Description: Template of the PRISMA chart to be used to register the flow of literature records along the different phases of the systematic review linked to the PIF database. For every systematic review, three BibTeX files containing records post-deduplication, post-eligibility assessment and post-insertion will be uploaded on the Zenodo community.

Annex 3: PIF food categorisation system

Description: Food categorisation structure implemented in the PIF database

Food category	Food subcategory	Food class	Food subclass	Food class specie	
Composite dishes (A03VA)	Sandwiches, pizza and other stuffed bread-like cereal products (A03YY)	Sandwich and sandwich-like dishes (A03YZ)	Raw (#F28.A07HS)		
			Cooked (#F28.A0BA1)		
			NA (-)		
			Pizza and pizza-like dishes (A03ZN)	Raw (#F28.A07HS)	
				Cooked (#F28.A0BA1)	
				NA (-)	
			Savoury pies and tarts (A0CEN)	Raw (#F28.A07HS)	
				Cooked (#F28.A0BA1)	
				NA (-)	
			Finger food (A040C)	Raw (#F28.A07HS)	
			Cooked (#F28.A0BA1)		
			NA (-)		
	Pastas and rice (or other cereal) – based dishes (A040M)		Raw (#F28.A07HS)		
			Cooked (#F28.A0BA1)		
			NA (-)		
	Dishes excluding pasta or rice dishes, sandwiches and pizza (A03VC)	Meat based dishes (A03VV)	Raw (#F28.A07HS)		
			Cooked (#F28.A0BA1)		
			NA (-)		
		Fish and seafood based dishes (A03XJ)	Raw (#F28.A07HS)		
			Cooked (#F28.A0BA1)		
			NA (-)		
		Egg based dishes (A03YJ)	Raw (#F28.A07HS)		
			Cooked (#F28.A0BA1)		
			NA (-)		
		Potato based dishes (A03VD)	Raw (#F28.A07HS)		

		Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Legumes based dishes (A03VM)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Mushroom based dishes (A03YS)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Vegetable based dishes (A03XX)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Undefined dishes (A03VC)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
Soups (A041L)		Raw (#F28.A07HS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) Dried (#F28.A07KG) NA (-)
Salads (A042B)	Mixed vegetable salad (A042D)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Prepared mixed egg/meat/fish/vegetable salad (A042M)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Fruit salad (A01QG)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
Spoonable desserts and ice creams (A0C68)	Water-based sweet desserts (A04PD)	
	Dairy ice creams and similar (A02PZ)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pasteurised (#F28.A07HV) UHT (#F28.A07HY) NA (-)
	Other desserts spoonable (A04NS)	Raw (#F28.A07HS)

			Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)	
	UndefinedC (A03VA)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) Dried (#F28.A07KG) NA (-)		
Aquatic based food (-)	Crustaceans (A02FD)	Freshwater crustaceans (A02FE)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)	
		Crabs, sea-spiders (A02FL)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)	
		Lobsters, spiny-rock lobster (A0F9Z)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)	
		King crabs, squat- lobsters (A0FAA)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)	
		Shrimps and prawns (A02FX)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)	
		Krill, planktonic crustaceans (A02FM)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)	
		Miscellaneous marine crustaceans (A02FJ)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)	
		Molluscs (A02GM)	Freshwater molluscs (A02HY)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
			Abalones, winkles, conchs (A02GS)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
Oysters (A02HG)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS)			

		Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Mussels (A02HF)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Scallops, pectens (A02HN)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Clams, cockles, arkshells (A02GZ)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Squids, cuttlefishes, octopuses (A02HZ)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Miscellaneous marine molluscs (A0FAB)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
Other marine invertebrate (-)	Sea-squirts and other tunicates (A02GN)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Sea urchins and other echinoderms (A02GP)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Jellyfishes and similar (A02GY)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Undefined marine invertebrate (-)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
Fish (meat) (A026V)	Freshwater fish (A026X)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Diadromous fish (A028E)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS)

		Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Marine fish (A029R)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Undefined fish (A026V)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
Processed or preserved fish (including processed offal) (A02KB)	Structured/textured fish meat products or fish paste (A0EYV)	
	Fermented fish (A16FA)	
	Marinated/pickled fish (A0F0P)	
	Dried fish (A02JP)	
	Canned/jarred fish (A0EYR)	
	Smoked fish (A0EYS)	
	NA (A02KB)	
Offal (-)	Seafood offal (A16FR)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Fish liver (A02EJ)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Fish roe (A02EM)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
	Other fish offal (A02FB)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
Algae and prokaryotes	Green algae (A00VB)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS)

organisms (A00VA)	Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
Red algae (A00VE)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
Brown algae (A00VK)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
Other Algae (A0DCP)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
Micro-phyte (A04LX)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) NA (-)
UndefinedS (A0EZQ)	Raw (#F28.A07HS) Pre-cut (#F28.A07KS) Cooked (#F28.A0BA1) Fermented (#F28.A0CQZ) Textured (#F28. A07LM) Smoked (#F28.A07JV) NA (-)

Abbreviations

Composite: UndefinedC: Undefined composite foods that do not fit the other ‘Composite’ subcategories; **Seafood:** UndefinedS: Undefined seafood that do not fit the other ‘Seafood’ subcategories;;

Annex 4: Categorisation system of methods for relevant *Vibrio* spp (*Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, *Vibrio vulnificus*, *Vibrio cholerae* non-O1/non-O139)⁸

1. *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*

1. Detection assay

Enrichment/culture step

- ISO 21872-1:2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- Other methods: NMKL Method N°156, 1997 (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis); MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Canada)
- APW, one-step or two-step enrichment (with 6h initial enrichment step)
- None (direct plating)
- Other

Isolation media

- ISO 21872-1:2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- TCBS (thiosulfate citrate bile salts sucrose agar)
- CHROMagar™ *Vibrio* (CV)
- Other

Identification (for prevalence: presence/absence)

- ISO 21872-1:2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- Biochemical identification
 - AGS
 - OX
 - Halotolerance test
 - String test
 - Agglutination test
 - API20E
 - combination
- Molecular detection/identification (total Vp):
 - Conventional PCR (cPCR)
 - *tlh*
 - *toxR*
 - pR72H fragment
 - Other
 - Real-Time PCR (rt PCR)
 - *toxR*
 - *tlh*,
 - Other
- Multiplex cPCR (*tlh*, *tdh*, *trh*, *fla/other*)

⁸ Categorisation for methods shown in this Annex will be re-arranged to match methods structure of PIF.

- LAMP (loop-mediated isothermal amplification)
 - *tlh*, *rpoD* or *toxR*
 - Other
 - Colony / DNA probe hybridization (*tlh*)
 - Other
- MALDI TOF (mass spectrometry)
 - Other

2. Enumeration assay

Enrichment/culture step

- ISO 21872-2 2020 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- Other methods: MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Canada); NMKL Method N°156, 1997 (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis)
- MPN (APW, one-step enrichment)
- HGMF culture on filter (TSAMS medium)
- Direct plating – DNA hybridization (TSA medium)
- None
- Other

Isolation media

- ISO 21872-1:2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- TCBS (thiosulfate citrate bile salts sucrose agar)
- CHROMagar™ *Vibrio* (CV)
- None
- Other (VPSA for HGMF)

Identification

- ISO 21872-2:2020 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- Biochemical identification
 - AGS
 - OX
 - Halotolerance test
 - String test
 - Agglutination test
 - API20E
 - combination
- Molecular detection/identification (total Vp):
 - Conventional PCR (cPCR)
 - *tlh*
 - *toxR*
 - pR72H fragment
 - Other
 - Real-Time PCR (rt PCR)
 - *toxR*
 - other
 - Multiplex cPCR (*tlh*, *tdh*, *trh*, *fla*, other)

- Multiplex rt PCR (*tlh*, *tdh*, *trh*, *other*)
- LAMP (loop-mediated isothermal amplification)
 - *tlh*, *rpoD* or *toxR*
 - *other*
- Colony / DNA probe hybridization (*tlh*, *other*)
- MALDI TOF (mass spectrometry)
- Other

3. Pathogenicity determination

- ISO 21872-2 2020 (if mentioned)
- Kanagawa phenomenon (KP) on Wagatsuma agar
- Enterotoxigenic activity: fluid accumulation: (ileal loop)
- Molecular determination (enteropathogenic Vp):
 - cPCR : *tdh*, *trh*, ORF8, GS-PCR (*toxR* gene), T3SS
 - rt PCR: *tdh*
 - Multiplex cPCR: (*tlh*), *tdh*, *trh*
 - Multiplex rt PCR: (*tlh*), *tdh*, *trh*
 - LAMP: *tdh*, *trh1*, *trh2*
- Other
 - Explain other (free text)

4. Strain characterization (more than Vp or Vpp)

- WGS
- MLST/sequence typing
- PFGE
- Serotyping
- Other

2. *Vibrio vulnificus*

1. Detection assay

Enrichment/culture step

- ISO 21872-1 2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- Other methods: MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Canada); NMKL Method N°156, 1997 (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis)
- APW, one-step or two-step enrichment (with 6h initial enrichment step), salt None
- Other

Isolation media

- ISO 21872-1 2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- TCBS (thiosulfate citrate bile salts sucrose) agar
- CHROMagar™ *Vibrio*

- Colistin-Polymyxin B-cellobiose (CPC medium), mCPC, CC agars
- None (direct plating)
- Other

Identification (for prevalence: presence/absence)

- ISO 21872-1 2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- Biochemical identification
 - AGS
 - OX
 - Halotolerance test
 - String test
 - Agglutination test
 - API20E
 - combination
- Molecular detection/identification:
 - Conventional PCR (cPCR):
 - *vvH*
 - Other: *dnaJ*
 - Real-Time PCR (rt PCR):
 - *vvhA*
 - Other: *vvp*
 - LAMP (loop mediated isothermal amplification): *rpoS*
 - Colony / DNA probe hybridization (*vvhA*)
 - other
- MALDI TOF (mass spectrometry)

2. Enumeration assay

Enrichment/culture step

- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- Other methods: MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Canada); NMKL Method N°156, 1997 (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis)
- MPN (APW, one-step enrichment)
- Direct plating
- Other

Isolation media

FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)

- Other methods: MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Canada); NMKL Method N°156, 1997 (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis)
- TCBS
- mCPC, CC agars
- CHROMagar™ *Vibrio*

Identification

- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- Other methods: MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Canada); NMKL Method N°156, 1997 (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis)
- Biochemical identification:
 - AGS

- OX
 - Halotolerance
 - String test
 - Agglutination test
 - API20E
 - Combination
 - Other
- Molecular detection/identification:
 - Conventional PCR (cPCR):
 - *vvH*
 - Other: *dnaJ*
 - Real-Time PCR (rt PCR):
 - *vvhA*
 - Other: *vvp*
 - LAMP (loop mediated isothermal amplification): *rpoS*
 - Colony / DNA probe hybridization (*vvhA*)
- MALDI TOF (mass spectrometry)

3. Pathogenicity determination

- Molecular determination
 - cPCR : *vvhA*
 - rt PCR
 - *vvhA*
 - Other: *vuuA, pilF, vcgC, hly*
- Other :
 - Explain other (free text)

4. Strain characterization

- WGS
- MLST/sequence typing
- PFGE
- Other

3. *Vibrio cholerae non-O1/non-139*

1. Detection assay

Enrichment/culture step

- ISO 21872-1:2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: *Vibrio* (2004) (if mentioned)
- Other methods: NMKL Method N°156, 1997 (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis); MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Canada)
- APW, one-step or two-step enrichment (with 6h initial enrichment step)
- None
- Other

Isolation media

- ISO 21872-1:2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: Vibrio (2004) (if mentioned)
- Other methods: NMKL Method N°156, 1997 (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis); MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Canada)
- TCBS (thiosulfate citrate bile salts sucrose agar)
- CHROMagar™ Vibrio
- None
- Other

Identification (for prevalence: presence/absence)

- ISO 21872-1:2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: Vibrio (2004) (if mentioned)
- Other methods: NMKL Method N°156, 1997 (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis); MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Canada)
- Biochemical identification:
 - AGS
 - OX
 - Halotolerance test
 - String test
 - Agglutination test O 1
 - Agglutination test O 139
 - Agglutination test O1 and O139
 - O/129 sensitivity
 - API20E
 - Combination
- Molecular identification:
 - cPCR :
 - 16S-23S rRNA ITS, prVC
 - other *toxR*, *ompW*
 - rt PCR
 - 16S-23S rRNA ITS (ISR)
 - other
- LAMP (loop mediated isothermal amplification) : *ompW*
- MALDI TOF (mass spectrometry)

2. Enumeration assay

No standardised/official method available for the enumeration assay for *V. cholerae* non-O1/non-O139.

Enrichment/culture step

- MPN (APW, one-step enrichment)
- Direct plating
- Other

Isolation media

- ISO 21872-1:2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: Vibrio (2004) (if mentioned)

- Other methods: NMKL Method N°156, 1997 (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis); MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Canada)
- TCBS (thiosulfate citrate bile salts sucrose agar)
- CHROMagar™ Vibrio
- None
- Other

Identification

- ISO 21872-1:2017 (if mentioned)
- FDA-BAM chapter 9: Vibrio (2004) (if mentioned)
- Other methods: NMKL Method N°156, 1997 (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis); MFLP-37 (Oct. 2006 – Canada)
- Biochemical identification:
 - o AGS
 - o OX
 - o Halotolerance test
 - o String test
 - o Agglutination test (O1/O139)
 - o O/129 sensitivity
 - o API20E
 - o Combination
 - o Other
- Molecular identification:
 - o cPCR :
 - 16S-23S rRNA ITS, prVC
 - *toxR*, *ompW*
 - *Other*
 - o rt PCR
 - 16S-23S rRNA ITS (ISR)
 - Other
 - o LAMP (loop mediated isothermal amplification) :
 - o *ompW*
 - o Other
- MALDI TOF (mass spectrometry)
- Other

3. Pathogenicity determination

- Molecular determination:
 - o cPCR :
 - *ctxAB*,
 - *ctxA*,
 - *ctxB*
 - Other: *zot*, *ace*, *tcp*, *rfbO1*, *rfbO139*
 - *Combination+text*
- Other :
 - o Explain other (free text)
 - o Enterotoxigenicity (Y-1 mouse adrenal cell assay, immunoassay for CT), Beta hemolysis

4. Strain characterization (*non-O1/non –O139*)

- WGS
- MLST/sequence typing
- PFGE
- Serotyping
- Other
- Multiplex rt PCR (*Vp, toxR; Vv, vvhA; Vc, sodB*)